

This is the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in SynLett

ULTRASOUND-ASSISTED CONJUGATE ADDITION OF ORGANOMETALLIC REAGENTS TO 3-DIETHYLPHOSPHONOCOUMARIN

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ABSTRACT: Ultrasonic activation is not a traditional method of heat transfer in organic chemistry but it has major advantage over the common methods by reducing the energy consumption for accomplishing the process. Sonication can be applied in different types of organic reactions. Here we present a comparative investigation on 1,4-conjugate addition of nucleophiles to 2H-1-benzopyran-2-one derivatives under common and ultrasound conditions.

KEY WORDS: 1,4-CONJUGATE ADDITION, COUMARINS, ORGANOMETALLIC REAGENTS, PHOSPHONATES.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ultrasonic irradiation has been introduced as an excellent alternative to thermal energy in promoting organic reactions, especially those requiring severe conditions [1,2,3]. It is known that this kind of energy is used to generate radicals and to initiate electron-transfer process during the organic reactions. Ultrasound technique is also used as an eco-environmental technology in green chemistry and provides another option for improving the common reactions that require high temperatures, longer reaction times and unsatisfactory yields [4].

Sonication provides an unusual mechanism to generate high-energy chemistry due to the extraordinary temperatures and pressure generated by the cavitation bubble collapse. The process depends on cavitation and characteristic of the bubbles. The definition of cavitation can be given as the formation and the behavior of gas,

vapor bubbles, or bubble clouds in a liquid and is induced through a pressure fall in a flow [5,6,7,8]. In some cases, the collapsed bubbles can carry smaller particles causing shocks among them and possibly causing surface amorphication which may result in their sintering. The best news for the organic chemists is that these localized hot spots operate as microreactors wherein sound energy is modified into useful form of chemical energy [9,10].

There are many examples of metal-mediated organic reactions that have been accelerated under ultrasound due to the metal surface activation which is an efficient method for removing impurities and oxidized layers. Meanwhile it can reduce the particle size and bring about modified surfaces of the metal and at the same time speeds up the formation of organometallic reagents [4].

Michael reaction is frequently a first choice chemical reaction in organic synthesis due to the vast variety of Michael's acceptors and nucleophiles that could be applied. Most of the time, the reaction can be easily accomplished by using simple experimental procedures. It is well known that the conjugate addition (1,4 addition) of enolates to α,β -unsaturated acceptors is one of the fundamental and important methods for formation of carbon-carbon bonds [11]. Therefore in synthesis the impact of Michael reaction derives from the fact that mostly any activated alkene can serve as an acceptor e.g. α,β -unsaturated ketones, aldehydes, amides, acids, lactones, phosphonates, phosphoranes, quinones, coumarins, etc. [12,13,14,15,16]. Also this specific type of addition allows large numbers of hard and soft nucleophiles to react with the selected acceptors although competitive 1,2-addition reaction could be expected. Moreover, using that conception, it is possible to form multiple stereogenic centers within a molecule in a single synthetic step. Additional benefits are mild reaction conditions, high functional group tolerance, short reaction times and less toxic precursors [17].

A number of studies on 1,4-conjugate addition reaction of nucleophiles to unsaturated carbonyl compounds have reported a necessity of basic or acid catalysts [18]. Frequently those conditions have involved side reactions, for example, polymerization of the activated alkenes especially in acid conditions. In other methods when sensitive substrates are used the stoichiometric ratios of the reagents applied in the reactions have been controlled in order to avoid extra products [19]. Nowadays one of the reliable approaches for successful conjugate addition is based on the effect of ultrasound waves [20].

Previous studies in our research group have presented [15,21,22,23,24] 3-substituted 2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyrans as alternative acceptors in 1,4-conjugate addition with varieties of nucleophiles and in tandem reactions. In the present work, we wish to introduce our subsequent investigations on the chemical behavior of 3-diethylphosphonocoumarin employed in ultrasound-assisted Michael type reaction. Another important subject that needs to be mentioned is the regioselectivity of the reaction during the addition step – preferred conformation around C3-C4 bond in the product. A series of organometallic compounds were chosen as hard nucleophiles to interact with the coumarin system.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.1. Conjugate addition of organometallic reagents to diethyl 3-phosphonocoumarin

The overall driving force for the conjugate addition is the enthalpic change that accompanies replacement of a π -bond with σ -bonds. Thus, there is a preference for 1,4-addition over 1,2-addition. A large number of scientists have examined the effects of temperature, solvents and reaction time on the ratio of the products of 1,4-addition *versus* 1,2-addition [11,13,14,17,18]. Their results show that in general 1,2-addition is kinetically favored and therefore predominate at low temperature and in less polar solvents, whereas 1,4-addition is thermodynamically favored and predominates at 25 °C or higher [11]. Another aspect [25] is theoretical evaluation of the local reactivity of electrophilic centers C2 and C4 in the 3-substituted coumarins system (**Scheme 1**) using atomic charges, atomic electrostatic potential, XPS binding energies and atomic Fukui indices. This type of analysis had shown that coumarins would preferably react with soft nucleophiles at position 2 and with hard nucleophiles at position 4.

Scheme 1. R = Et, *n*-Pr, *i*-Pr, CH₂Ph, CH₂COOEt, CH₂COO*t*-Bu; M = Mg, Zn; X = Br, Cl

A conjugate addition of different organometallic reagents to diethyl ester of 2-oxo-2*H*-1-benzopyran-3-phosphonic acid **1** was carried out under reflux and 1,4-products **2** to **7** were isolated with yields that varied between 38 and 78% (**Scheme 1**, **Table 1**). The needed organometallic compounds were prepared at classical conditions (heating) using dry diethyl ether. The reaction easily took place with formation of the preferred *trans* isomer **2a** as it could be expected for the chemical behavior of benzopyrans from our previous studies (**Scheme 2**). However, during our investigations we came across one main problem applying the common condition for conjugate addition of organometallics. It was the lack of reproducibility of the results in the performed reactions, the yield for each product deviated up to 30%.

Scheme 2. Possible products of conjugate addition.

Earlier we had applied [23] ultrasonic irradiation on conjugate addition of phosphites to several coumarin systems. The results emphasized on the increase of reaction velocity and yields of the products. The present study provides more evidences for the effect of sonication on the reaction between preformed organometallic compounds and diethyl ester of 2-oxo-2*H*-benzopyran-3-phosphonic acid **1** (**Scheme 1**). This method gave us the opportunity to overcome the lack of reproducibility and to use simpler experimental set up in mild conditions. Moreover, the usage of ultrasound waves made the formation of the needed organometallic compounds faster than when heat was used as a form of energy. Because of the ultrasound activation the Michael reaction was accomplished faster and proceeded with excellent yields.

Table 1. Reaction conditions for addition of organometallic reagents to 3-phosphonocoumarin **1** under Michael reaction conditions.

Compound	Substituent	Metal	Halogen	Reaction conditions RMX : coumarin : solvent	Reaction time (US) [min]	Yields, [%]	
						US ^a	Reflux ^a
2	Et	Mg	Br	3 : 1 : Et ₂ O/ CH ₂ (OCH ₃) ₂	10	89	64
3	<i>n</i> -Pr	Mg	Br	3 : 1 : Et ₂ O/ CH ₂ (OCH ₃) ₂	30	94	77
4	<i>i</i> -Pr	Mg	Br	3 : 1 : Et ₂ O/ CH ₂ (OCH ₃) ₂	50	74	69
5	PhCH ₂	Mg	Cl	3 : 1 : Et ₂ O/ CH ₂ (OCH ₃) ₂	90	53	38
6	CH ₂ COOEt	Zn	Br	3 : 1 : Et ₂ O/ CH ₂ (OCH ₃) ₂	80	85	-
7	CH ₂ COO <i>t</i> -Bu	Mg	Cl	3 : 1 : Et ₂ O/ CH ₂ (OCH ₃) ₂	30	95	78

a – Method A-D in **Part 5**.

The chemical behavior of 3-diethylphosphonocoumarin **1** under sonication was studied by tracking the steric effect of the added alkyl groups. Results of the further investigation of compound **1** with organomagnesium or organozinc compounds are listed in **Table 1** comparing the yields of reactions with or without ultrasonic irradiation. All reactions were performed in a mixture of dry ethyl ether and dry dimethoxymethane keeping the temperature at 40°C. The raw products were purified by column chromatography or recrystallization.

It can be seen from **Table 1** that when bulkier groups are used the reaction times get larger but never the less the yields of the products are high. The same correlation was observed when the metal was changed to Zn. It can also be assumed that when bromides are implied, the reaction time will be shorter than when chlorides are used.

2.2. Stereochemistry of the products and reaction path

Regarding the stereochemistry of the studied reaction we could suggest an attack of the nucleophile from least hindered side of the C3=C4 double bond, as shown in **Scheme 3**. The reaction could be classified as *syn*-addition because nucleophile and electrophile approach the same side of the C3=C4 bond. Moreover, the isolated products are with antiperiplanar aligned bulkier groups to the C3-C4 bond.

Scheme 3. Proposed reaction mechanism.

In previous investigations [21,26,27] a predominant conformation of the final product of the reaction between 3-phenyl-, 3-methyl- or 3-diethylphosphonocoumarins and organometallic reagents was given. NMR Data presented values of the vicinal H3-H4 coupling constant between 2 and 3 Hz which indicates for isolation only of the *trans*-gosh isomer. Therefore the authors assumed conformers with axial-pseudoaxial location of the substituents to C-3 and C-4 atoms. Another study [24], showed the 1,4-conjugate addition of nitromethane to 3-diethylphosphonocoumarin **1**. It was found that there was a *trans* configuration and a torsion angle of 90° between the H3 and H4 atoms. Thus, the two bulkier groups again are aligned in antiperiplanar position and they are more close to each other comparing with the isomers obtained from 3-alkyl or 3-phenylsubstituted coumarins, which means torsion angle differ from 180 degrees. In this study the *trans* configuration was also confirmed by X-ray spectroscopy.

Present research on the conjugate addition of organometallic reagents to 3-diethylphosphonocoumarin **1** requires a complete examination on the configuration of the isolated products on the base of NMR spectral data and comparison with above-mentioned results. In **Table 2** are presented chemical shifts of the resonance peaks for H3 and H4 protons of the compounds **2** to **7**, which are mainly altered. Spin-spin interactions between these two protons give essential information for the conformational preferences in the isolated products and also are included in **Table 2**. The vicinal coupling constant of H3-H4 protons in the isolated compounds this time has value of 1 Hz from which it was assumed a dihedral angle of 70 - 80 degrees (**Scheme 4**). This value of the angle confirms the formation of *trans* isomer in all reaction conditions when a nucleophilic addition to 3-substituted coumarins

take place. Again bulkier groups around C3-C4 bond have preferred antiperiplanar arrangement. Comparing the configurations of the compounds obtained in the previous studies, obviously small substituents in 3 position in the coumarin system set the configuration to the *trans*-gosh with typical angle of 60 degrees, whereas the presence of phosphonic and nitromethyl groups change the conformation with dihedral angle between H3 and H4 of 90 degrees. Regarding which the spin-spin interactions of H4 proton with neighbored CH₂ group vicinal constants of 6.1 to 7.9 Hz were measured. Also on interest are vicinal ³J_{PH} constants with values up to 15 Hz proving *cis* configuration between phosphorus atom from the phosphonic group and H4 proton.

Table 2. Chemical shifts and coupling constants for the H3 and H4 atoms.

Substituent	H ₃ , δ [ppm]	³ J _{H3H4} [Hz]	² J _{PH3} [Hz]	H ₄ , δ [ppm]	³ J _{H4R} [Hz]	³ J _{PH4} [Hz]
H ^a	3.35			3.37		
Et	3.41	1.0	25.5	3.33	7.6	13.5
<i>n</i> -Pr	3.39	1.0	25.1	3.33	7.6	13.5
<i>i</i> -Pr	3.45	0.9	24.6	3.27	6.1	15.4
PhCH ₂	3.41	1.0	24.7	3.68	7.9	13.3
CH ₂ COOEt	3.57	1.0	25.9	3.82	7.3	13.8
CH ₂ COO <i>t</i> -Bu	3.55	0.9	25.9	3.80	7.4	14.3
CH ₂ NO ₂ ^a	3.55	0.3	26.2	4.26	7.1	13.9

a - Reference [15,24].

Anisotropy effect of PhCH₂- and CH₂COOR ester groups on the chemical shifts of methyl and methylene groups from one of the POCH₂CH₃ moiety, as well as H4 proton is also noticeable. The alignment of phenyl group causes a low-frequency shift of 0.03 ppm for one of POCH₂CH₃ group and high-frequency shift of 0.35 ppm for H4 when values for compounds **2** and **5** were compared. Opposite effect have ester groups with shift of resonances to the high-frequency in both cases (0.05 and 0.5 ppm).

Scheme 4. Conformational analysis on coupling constants of H3 and H4.

The assumptions from NMR spectra are in agreement with the structure given from X-ray of the diethyl (4-isopropyl-2-oxochroman-3-yl) phosphonate **4**. The single crystal X-ray diffraction had confirmed that the final product of the 1,4-conjugate addition is one of the possible diastereomers – *trans* isomer. As shown in **Figure 1**,

the dihedral angles of H4-C4-C3-H3 and CH₂-C4-C3-P1, determined from the molecular structure in the crystal displaying values of 73.69° and 162.87°, confirm the pseudoaxial antiperiplanar disposition of the two bulkier groups.

Figure 1. Molecular structures of compound **4** in the crystal. ORTEP representation with thermal ellipsoids.

Table 3. Crystal data and structure refinement for compound **4**.

Crystal parameters		Crystal parameters		Crystal parameters	
Empirical formula	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₅ P	c/Å	22.751(4)	F(000)	696.0
Formula weight	326.31	α/°	90	Crystal size/mm ³	0.5 × 0.5 × 0.08
Temperature/K	300.15	β/°	96.817(7)	Radiation	MoKα (λ=0.71073)
Crystal system	monoclinic	γ/°	90	Goodness of fit on F ²	0.936
Space group	P 2 ₁ /n	Volume/Å ³	1703.7(5)	Data/restraints/parameters	3011/0/204
a/Å	7.9389(15)	Z	4	final R indices (I > 2σ(I))	0.0634
b/Å	9.4994(16)	μ/mm ⁻¹	0.181	R indices (all data)	0.1246

3. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we have reported the application of common and sonicated conditions for the reaction of diethyl ester of 2-oxo-2*H*-1-benzopyran-3-phosphonic acid **1** with organometallic compounds. Michael type addition proceeds with better yields and shorter reaction time when ultrasound irradiation was applied. This approach enables the usage of simpler experimental set ups and mild reaction conditions characterized additionally with excellent reproducibility of the results.

Importantly, the method is useful for the preparation of 3,4-disubstituted chromanes with exact configuration on the C3-C4 bond. The stereochemistry of the products **2-7** was determined by NMR spectroscopy and X-ray spectra of product **4**. The general conclusion from the spectral data is that all products are isolated as *trans* isomers with pseudoaxial antiperiplanar disposition of bulkier groups in 3-th and 4-rd position. The compared coupling constants of spin-spin interaction of H3-H4 protons confirmed the formation of *trans* isomer in all reaction conditions when a nucleophilic addition to 3-substituted coumarins take place.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thanks to the colleagues from Laboratory of Molecular Spectroscopy of Structural Analysis, University of Sofia for the X-ray analysis.

5. EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points were determined with a Kofler hot-stage apparatus and are used without correction. The IR spectra were recorded with a Specord IR 71, IR 75 spectrophotometer. ^1H -, ^{13}C - and ^{31}P -NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance III 500 (at 500 MHz for ^1H , 125.7 MHz for ^{13}C and 202.4 MHz for ^{31}P , respectively) and Bruker AM 300 (at 300 MHz for ^1H and 75.4 MHz for ^{13}C , respectively) spectrometers. Chemical shifts are given in ppm downfield from tetramethylsilane as internal standard with deuteriochloroform as solvent. ^{31}P -NMR spectra were recorded with 85% H_3PO_4 as an external standard. The mass spectra were performed on a 70 eV with VG TS-250 spectrometer. Reactions were monitored by TLC on silica gel 60 F_{254} . Column chromatography was carried out on silica gel (Merck 0.063-0.2 mm and 0.043-0.063 mm) using as eluent *n*-hexane/EtOAc and methylene chloride/EtOAc mixtures with increasing polarity. Elemental analyses of C, H and N were carried out in the Laboratory of Elemental Analysis at the Department of Organic Chemistry, University of Sofia. The X-ray analysis was performed on Bruker Apex-II CCD diffractometer at the Laboratory of Molecular Spectroscopy of Structural Analysis, University of Sofia. The crystal was kept at 300.15 K during the collection. Using Olex2 [28], the structure was solved with ShelXS [29] structure solution program using "Direct Methods" and refined with the ShelXL [29] refinement package using "Least Squares" minimizations.

All chemical reagents were purchased from Merck and Fluka. The starting 3-substituted 2-oxo-2*H*-1-benzopyran **1** was prepared according to a procedure worked out in our laboratory [30].

General procedure

Method A: To an ether solution of organomagnesium compound, prepared from the corresponded alkyl halide (0.003 mol), magnesium (0.009 g, 0.0037 mol) and dry ethyl ether (7 ml) under reflux, was added a solution of 3-phosphonocoumarin **1** (0.28 g, 0.001 mol) in methylal. The reaction was carried out until the coumarin **1** was consumed (TLC-monitoring). The reaction mixture was poured onto 2N solution of hydrochloric acid and ice, extracted with dichloromethane, and the organic extracts were washed several times with water and later dried with anhydrous sodium sulfate. After the evaporation of the solvent the residue was recrystallized or purified by column chromatography as an eluent system *n*-hexane/EtOAc mixture (with increasing polarity) was used.

Method B: Method B is closely the same as method A but preparation of the organometallic compound and the reaction were carried out under ultrasound irradiation.

Method C: To an ether solution of the organozinc compound, prepared from ethyl bromoacetate (0.0024 mol), zinc (0.157 g, 0.0024 mol) and dry ethyl ether (5 ml) irradiated with ultrasound for 90 minutes, was added a solution of 3-phosphonocoumarin (0.28g, 0.001 mol). The reaction was carried out under ultrasonic irradiation until the starting materials were consumed (TLC-monitoring). The reaction mixture was poured onto 2N solution of

hydrochloric acid and ice, extracted with dichloromethane, and the organic extracts were washed several times with water and later dried with anhydrous sodium sulfate. After the evaporation of the solvent the residue was recrystallized (*n*-hexane/ether).

Method D: To an ether solution of the organomagnesium compound, prepared from *i*-propyl chloride (0.01 mol) and magnesium (0.01 mol, 0.24 g), irradiated with ultrasound for 30 minutes, a solution of *t*-butyl acetate (0.007 mol) in dry diethyl ether was added. Reaction mixture was sonicated for additional 60 minutes. A solution of 3-phosphonocoumarin **1** (0.7g, 0.0025 mol) was then added to the reaction mixture. The reaction was carried out under ultrasonic irradiation until the coumarin **1** was consumed (TLC-monitoring). The reaction mixture was poured onto 2N solution of hydrochloric acid and ice, extracted with dichloromethane, and the organic extracts were washed several times with water and later dried with anhydrous sodium sulfate. After the evaporation of the solvent the residue was recrystallized (*n*-hexane/ether).

Diethyl (4-ethyl-2-oxochroman-3-yl) phosphonate (2) – Method B. The product was recrystallized from *n*-hexane/dichloromethane: 0.28 g. 89%, white crystals, mp = 86 - 88 °C.

IR (CHCl₃): $\nu = 1035, 1775 \text{ cm}^{-1}$

¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) $\delta = 7.27$ (td, $J = 7.7, 1.4$, 1H, H-7), 7.22 (dd, $J = 7.5, 1.6$ Hz, 1H, H-5), 7.13 (td, $J = 7.5, 1.1$ Hz, 1H, H-8), 7.04 (dd, $J = 8.1, 1.1$ Hz, 1H, H-6), 4.12 (dq, $J = 14.2, 7.4, 7.1$ Hz, 2H, POCH₂CH₃), 3.76 (dq, $J = 10.0, 7.1$ Hz, 1H, POCH_AH_BCH₃), 3.41 (dd, $J = 25.5, 1.0$ Hz, 1H, H-3), $3.37 - 3.46$ (m, 1H, POCH_AH_BCH₃), $3.30 - 3.36$ (dt, $J = 13.5, 7.6$ Hz, 1H, H-4) $1.60-1.66$ (m, 2H, 4-CH₂CH₃), 1.33 (t, $^3J = 7.1$ Hz, 3H, POCH₂CH₃), 0.94 (t, $^3J = 7.4$ Hz, 3H, 4-CH₂CH₃), 0.89 (t, $^3J = 7.1$ Hz, 3H, POCH₂CH₃).

¹³C NMR (125.7 MHz, CDCl₃) $\delta = 164.1$ (d, $J = 6.1$ Hz, C-2), 151.1 (s, C-8a), 128.9 (s, C-7), 128.6 (s, C-5), 124.5 (s, C-8), 124.0 (s, C-4a), 116.7 (s, C-6), 63.2 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 62.9 (d, $J = 7.0$ Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 45.6 (d, $J = 127.9$ Hz, C-3), 38.8 (d, $J = 4.4$ Hz, C-4), 30.1 (d, $J = 17.6$ Hz, 4-CH₂CH₃), 16.2 (d, $J = 6.2$ Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 15.9 (d, $J = 6.2$ Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 11.0 (s, 4-CH₂CH₃).

³¹P NMR (202.4 MHz, CDCl₃) $\delta = 18.78$ (s).

MS: m/z (%) = 312(M⁺) (62), 283 (70), 255 (56), 227 (76), 209 (70), 175 (100), 147 (78), 138 (63), 118 (75), 91 (85).

Anal. (C, H): calculated C = 58.05%, H = 6.18%; found C = 57.79%, H = 6.48%.

Diethyl (2-oxo-4-propylchroman-3-yl) phosphonate (3) – Method B. The product was purified by column chromatography using *n*-hexane/EtOAc: 0.3 g. 94 %, colorless liquid.

IR (CHCl₃): $\nu = 1020, 1770 \text{ cm}^{-1}$

¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) $\delta = 7.27$ (td, $J = 8.0, 1.6$, 1H, H-7), 7.21 (dd, $J = 7.5, 1.6$ Hz, 1H, H-5), 7.12 (td, $J = 7.4, 1.1$ Hz, 1H, H-8), 7.04 (dd, $J = 8.1, 1.0$ Hz, 1H, H-6), 4.11 (dq, $J = 14.1, 7.7, 7.1$ Hz, 2H, POCH₂CH₃), 3.76 (dq, $J = 10.0, 7.1$ Hz, 1H, POCH_AH_BCH₃), 3.39 (dd, $J = 25.1, 1.0$ Hz, 1H, H-3), $3.38 - 3.49$ (m, 1H, POCH_AH_BCH₃), $3.30 - 3.36$ (dt, $J = 13.5, 7.6$ Hz, 1H, H-4) $1.54-1.58$ (m, 2H, 4-CH₂CH₂CH₃), $1.29-1.41$ (m, 2H, 4-CH₂CH₂CH₃), 1.32 (td, $^3J = 7.1, 0.4$ Hz, 3H, POCH₂CH₃), 0.91 (t, $^3J = 7.3$ Hz, 3H, 4-CH₂CH₃), 0.89 (td, $^3J = 6.8, 0.2$ Hz, 3H, POCH₂CH₃).

¹³C NMR (125.7 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 163.9 (d, *J* = 6.1 Hz, C-2), 151.1 (s, C-8a), 128.7 (s, C-7), 128.4 (s, C-5), 124.5 (s, C-8), 124.3 (s, C-4a), 116.6 (s, C-6), 63.1 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 62.8 (d, *J* = 7.1 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 45.7 (d, *J* = 127.8 Hz, C-3), 39.0 (d, *J* = 17.0 Hz, C-4), 37.0 (d, *J* = 4.2 Hz, 4-CH₂CH₂CH₃), 19.5 (s, 4-CH₂CH₂CH₃), 16.1 (d, *J* = 6.2 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 15.8 (d, *J* = 6.1 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 13.6 (s, 4-CH₂CH₂CH₃).

³¹P NMR (202.4 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 18.75 (s).

MS: *m/z* (%) = 326(M⁺) (16), 283 (32), 255 (16), 227 (52), 209 (37), 189 (100), 147 (59), 111 (43), 91 (45).

Anal. (C, H): calculated C = 58.89%, H = 7.10%; found C = 58.93%, H = 7.25%.

Diethyl (4-isopropyl-2-oxochroman-3-yl) phosphonate (4) – Method B. The product was recrystallized *n*-hexane/dichloromethane: 0.24 g 74 %, white crystals, mp = 55 - 57 °C.

IR (CHCl₃): ν = 1030, 1775 cm⁻¹

¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 7.27 (td, *J* = 7.4, 1.7, 1H, H-7), 7.21 (dd, *J* = 7.6, 1.7 Hz, 1H, H-5), 7.12 (td, *J* = 7.3, 1.2 Hz, 1H, H-8), 7.04 (dd, *J* = 8.1, 1.1 Hz, 1H, H-6), 4.13 (dq, *J* = 14.2, 8.0, 7.1 Hz, 2H, POCH₂CH₃), 3.80 (dq, *J* = 10.0, 7.1 Hz, 1H, POCH_AH_BCH₃), 3.45 (dd, *J* = 24.6, 0.9 Hz, 1H, H-3), 3.31 – 3.48 (m, 1H, POCH_AH_BCH₃), 3.27 (dd, *J* = 15.4, 6.1 Hz, 1H, H-4) 1.84-1.91 (m, 1H, 4-CH(CH₃)₂), 1.32 (td, ³*J* = 7.0, 0.6 Hz, 3H, POCH₂CH₃), 0.95 (d, ³*J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H, 4-CH(CH₃)₂), 0.91 (td, ³*J* = 7.0, 0.5 Hz, 3H, POCH₂CH₃), 0.90 (d, ³*J* = 6.7 Hz, 3H, 4-CH(CH₃)₂).

¹³C NMR (125.7 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 164.5 (d, *J* = 6.1 Hz, C-2), 151.6 (s, C-8a), 129.7 (s, C-7), 128.6 (s, C-5), 124.4 (s, C-8), 122.6 (s, C-4a), 116.5 (s, C-6), 63.2 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 62.9 (d, *J* = 6.9 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 43.30 (d, *J* = 125.5 Hz, CH-3), 43.32 (d, *J* = 7.0 Hz, CH-4), 34.4 (d, *J* = 15.9 Hz, 4-CH(CH₃)₂), 19.29 (s, 4-CH(CH₃)₂), 19.27 (s, 4-CH(CH₃)₂), 16.2 (d, *J* = 6.2 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 15.9 (d, *J* = 6.1 Hz, POCH₂CH₃).

³¹P NMR (202.4 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 19.75 (s).

MS: *m/z* (%) = 326(M⁺) (19), 283 (36), 255 (17), 227 (39), 209 (24), 189 (100), 147 (77), 118 (55), 91 (57).

Anal. (C, H): calculated C = 58.87%, H = 7.11%; found C = 58.79%, H = 6.89%.

Diethyl (4-benzyl-2-oxochroman-3-yl) phosphonate (5) – Method B. The product was recrystallized from *n*-hexane/dichloromethane: 0.2 g 53 % pale yellow crystals, mp = 83 - 85 °C.

IR (CHCl₃): ν = 1030, 1780 cm⁻¹.

¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 7.22 - 7.30 (m, 4H), 7.03 – 7.06 (m, 4H), 7.00 (dd, *J* = 7.7, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 4.03 (dq, *J* = 14.2, 7.1 Hz, 1H, POCH₂CH₃), 3.69 – 3.77 (m, 1H, POCH_AH_BCH₃), 3.68 (dt, *J* = 13.3, 7.9 Hz, 1H, H-4), 3.41 (dd, *J* = 24.7, 1.0 Hz, 1H, H-3), 3.35-3.43 (m, 1H, POCH_AH_BCH₃), 2.93 (ddd, *J* = 13.7, 7.1, 2.2 Hz, 1H, CH₂Ph), 2.78 (dd, *J* = 13.7, 8.8 Hz, 1H, CH₂Ph), 1.25 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 3H, POCH₂CH₃), 0.87 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 3H, POCH₂CH₃).

¹³C NMR (125.7 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 163.6 (d, *J* = 6.3 Hz, C-2), 151.2 (s, C-8a), 136.7 (s, C-1'), 129.4 (s, C-2' C-6'), 128.72 (s, C-7), 128.69 (s, C-3', C-5'), 128.72 (s, C-5), 127.1 (s, C-4'), 124.6 (s, C-8), 123.6 (s, C-4a), 116.6 (s, C-6), 63.2 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 62.9 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 44.3 (d, *J* = 128.0 Hz, C-3), 43.15 (d, *J* = 17.4 Hz, CH₂Ph), 39.2 (d, *J* = 4.0 Hz, C-4), 16.1 (d, *J* = 6.2 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 15.8 (d, *J* = 6.2 Hz, POCH₂CH₃).

³¹P NMR (202.4 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 18.43 (s).

MS: *m/z* (%) = 374(M⁺) (6), 283 (83), 255 (32), 237 (92), 196 (90), 147 (100), 118 (48), 109 (69), 91 (85).

Anal. (C, H): calculated C = 64.17%, H = 6.19%; found C = 64.29%, H = 6.09%.

Ethyl 2-(3-(diethoxyphosphoryl)-2-oxochroman-4-yl) acetate (6) – Method C. The product was purified by column chromatography using *n*-hexane/EtOAc, 0.3 g, 85%, colorless liquid.

IR (CHCl₃): 1015, 1050, 1740, 1770 cm⁻¹.

¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 7.27 - 7.31 (m, 2H), 7.04 - 7.14 (m, 2H), 4.07- 4.17 (m, 4H, POCH₂CH₃ and COOCH₂CH₃), 3.97 - 3.99 (m, 1H, POCH_AH_BCH₃), 3.82 (dt, *J* = 13.8, 7.3 Hz, 1H, H-4), 3.57 (dd, *J* = 25.9, 1.0 Hz, 1H, H-3), 3.53-3.61 (m, 1H, POCH_AH_BCH₃), 2.62 (d, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H, 4-CH₂), 1.30 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H, POCH₂CH₃), 1.22 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H, COOCH₂CH₃), 0.96 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H, POCH₂CH₃).

¹³C NMR (125.7 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 170.1 (s, COOCH₂CH₃), 164.1 (d, *J* = 6.0 Hz, C-2), 151.1 (s, C-8a), 129.2 (s, C-7), 128.5 (s, C-5), 124.9 (s, C-8), 122.6 (s, C-4a), 116.8 (s, C-6), 63.3 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 62.9 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 60.8 (s, COOCH₂CH₃), 45.1 (d, *J* = 127.4 Hz, C-3), 40.9 (d, *J* = 17.8 Hz, CH-4), 33.2 (s, CH₂-4), 16.4 (d, *J* = 6.3 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 16.3 (d, *J* = 6.2 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 14.1 (s, COOCH₂CH₃).

³¹P NMR (202.4 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 18.20 (s).

Anal. (C, H): calculated C = 55.14%, H = 6.26%; found C = 54.58%, H = 5.92%.

Tert-Butyl 2-(3-(diethoxyphosphoryl)-2-oxochroman-4-yl) acetate (7) – Method D. The product was recrystallized from *n*-hexane/ diethyl ether: mp = 83 - 85 °C, 0.95 g.

IR (CHCl₃): 1030, 1050, 1740, 1780 cm⁻¹.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 7.24 - 7.31 (m, 2H),), 7.11 (td, *J* = 7.4, 1.0 Hz, 1H, H-8), 7.04 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H, H-6), 4.05- 4.17 (m, 4H, POCH₂CH₃), 3.86 - 3.97 (m, 1H, POCH_AH_BCH₃), 3.80 (dt, *J* = 14.3, 7.4 Hz, 1H, H-4), 3.55 (dd, *J* = 25.9, 0.9 Hz, 1H, H-3), 3.50 - 3.62 (m, 1H, POCH_AH_BCH₃), 2.51 (dd, *J* = 7.2, 0.3 Hz, 2H, 4-CH₂), 1.41 (s, 9H, COOC(CH₃)₃), 1.29 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H, POCH₂CH₃), 0.96 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 3H, POCH₂CH₃).

¹³C NMR (75.4 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 169.2 (s, COOC(CH₃)₃), 163.4 (d, *J* = 6.0 Hz, C-2), 151.3 (s, C-8a), 128.9 (s, C-7), 128.5 (s, C-5), 124.8 (s, C-8), 122.9 (s, C-4a), 116.7 (s, C-6), 81.6 (s, COOC(CH₃)₃), 63.2 (d, *J* = 6.2 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 62.9 (d, *J* = 6.2 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 45.2 (d, *J* = 127.8 Hz, C-3), 42.4 (d, *J* = 17.2 Hz, CH-4), 34.0 (d, *J* = 3.1 Hz, CH₂-4), 27.9 (s, COOC(CH₃)₃), 16.1 (d, *J* = 6.1 Hz, POCH₂CH₃), 15.4 (d, *J* = 5.9 Hz, POCH₂CH₃).

MS: *m/z* (%) = 399(M⁺) (22), 342 (32), 283 (26), 205 (100), 196 (9), 147 (20), 138 (25), 111 (16), 91 (10).

Anal. (C, H): calculated C = 57.27%, H = 6.83%; found, C = 57.39%, H = 7.14%.

Crystallographic data for the structures in this paper have been deposited in the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center as a supplementary publication (4, CCDC 1451549). Copies of the data can be obtained, free of charge, on application to CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB12 1EZ, U.K [fax: +44 1223 336033 or e-mail: deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk. The Supplemental Material file includes the CIF file of 4.

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